

Feasibility of adaptive teaching with technology: Which implementation conditions matter?

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive teaching is regarded to address students' heterogeneity in schools and to individually support their learning. Technology may help to teach adaptively. However, it is still unclear whether realizing adaptive teaching with technology is a feasible teaching practice in real-world classrooms. More importantly, it is an open question which boundary conditions constrain the feasibility of adaptive teaching with technology. We realized a four-year co-design-project in which researchers and teachers co-constructively developed adaptive teaching units (duration: 3–4 weeks) by deliberately integrating technology across secondary education. To assess the feasibility of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching, we followed a sequential-explanatory mixed-methods approach during the co-design-process. We combined a quantitative study ($N = 183$), investigating students' learning gains and potential moderators, and a qualitative study by means of semi-structured teacher interviews ($N = 3$) on implementation conditions of the adaptive teaching units. We observed that the teaching units were particularly beneficial for students with low prior knowledge and when they were highly adaptive to students' needs. Fine-grained qualitative findings indicated that formative assessments and consolidation phases were crucial for the feasibility of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching, as well as a parsimonious use of technologies. These findings indicate that the feasibility of adaptive teaching with technology depends on boundary conditions, highlighting the need for further support to unfold the potential of adaptive teaching.

1. Introduction

Adaptive teaching is considered as an effective way to address students' heterogeneity (e.g., prior knowledge) in the classroom (Corno, 2008). Educational technology can support teachers to teach adaptively. However, a large proportion of technological

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development and research only focused on specific technologies, such as adaptive learning systems (Keuning and van Geel, 2021; Kulik & Fletcher, 2016) or teacher dashboards (Molenaar & Knoop-van Campen, 2019; van Leeuwen et al., 2019). Although these approaches have been demonstrated to be effective (Hillmayr et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2014; Tissenbaum & Slotta, 2019), there is an educational practice gap: Prior research strongly focused on technology-enhanced learning (e.g., Fütterer et al., 2023; Lachner, Backfisch, & Franke, 2024; Scheiter, 2021; Scherer et al., 2019), however, without considering how technology can be integrated into the classroom in an effective way to increase students' learning (Lachner, Backfisch, & Franke, 2024; Scheiter, 2021). A generalizable framework is missing, that combines a general concept of adaptivity (Corno, 2008) with the use of technology and a clear focus on the complex interplay of classroom teaching.

To address this research gap, we realized a four-year co-design project, in which researchers and teachers jointly developed a framework for adaptive teaching with a focus on integrating available technology that incorporated ideas from educational practice and research (Roschelle et al., 2006). By realizing a co-constructive design process, this framework was adopted in twelve technology-supported adaptive teaching units (duration: 3–4 weeks) comprising several teachers, topics, and subjects of the German high school curriculum (e.g., physics, ethics).

To examine the feasibility of our adaptive teaching framework across contexts, we followed a ManyClasses approach (Fyfe et al., 2021; Lachner et al., 2021), and synthesized the findings of the single teaching units to investigate potential boundary conditions on the individual student-level (i.e., prior knowledge) and on the contextual classroom level (i.e., implementation fidelity, domain). Combining the co-design and the ManyClasses approach allowed us to obtain empirical evidence that is localized in different subjects and at the same time allows generalizing the underlying educational principles across contexts (see Lachner, Sibley, & Wagner, 2024).

We additionally conducted semi-structured interviews with three teachers, whose teaching units initiated very a) small, b) medium, or c) large students' knowledge gains to construct integrated teacher profiles and understand the underlying teacher conditions accounting for differences in the feasibility of adaptive teaching with technology.

1.1. Adaptive teaching

Adaptive teaching has been discussed in educational practice for several decades (Corno, 2008; Tetzlaff et al., 2021). The idea of adaptive teaching is to tailor teaching practices towards students' pre-requisites (Schmidt et al., 2021) to enhance their learning outcomes. Students have different cognitive (e.g., prior knowledge), meta-cognitive (e.g., monitoring one's own learning process), and motivational (e.g., interest) pre-requisites which require distinct instructional strategies (Hammer et al., 2021; Jonassen, 2005). In the context of adaptive teaching, learning not only comprises the accumulation of knowledge, which is often measured by learning gains, but also enhancements of self-regulation skills that enable students to monitor and regulate their learning strategies. Compared to traditional one-size-fits-all approaches, adaptive teaching radically changes the mode of teaching, as it puts students' needs in focus (Corno, 2008; Karst et al., 2022; Tetzlaff et al., 2021).

The potential benefits of adaptive teaching are discussed in line with empirical findings of one-to-one tutoring (Bloom et al., 1984; Chi et al., 2001; VanLehn, 2011; Wittwer et al., 2010) which demonstrated large learning gains compared to conventional classroom instruction. These beneficial effects are often explained by the fact that one-on-one settings allow to iteratively assess learning progress and provide interactive support during tutoring (Chi et al., 2001; Herppich et al., 2017) to help students approach their zone of proximal development (Vygotsky, 1978). Adaptive teaching is therefore conceptualized as a "scaling-up" implementation that adopts principles of tutoring and applies them to entire classroom situations (Tetzlaff et al., 2021).

Adaptive teaching comprises a reciprocal loop (Corno, 2008; Tetzlaff et al., 2021) that contains formative assessments, and micro- and macro adaptations: As initial *formative assessments*, students' pre-requisites (e.g., prior knowledge, self-regulation, motivation) are assessed which are relevant for students' learning processes. Based on the formative assessment, students receive *adaptations on a macro level* (Corno, 2008). One of the relatively robust aptitude-treatment-interaction findings that may be used for macro adaptations is the expertise-reversal-effect (Kalyuga, 2007). According to the expertise-reversal-effect, the effectiveness of instructional strategies (e.g., the availability of worked examples versus problem-solving) depends on the level of prior knowledge. Thus, teachers may provide materials and instructions of varying complexity for two or three groups differing in their prior knowledge: For instance, students with low prior knowledge or misconceptions may learn with worked examples, whereas students with high prior knowledge may be engaged in problem-solving activities (Fyfe & Rittle-Johnson, 2016; Nievelstein et al., 2013; Richter et al., 2016). Finally, *micro adaptations* refer to specific moment-to-moment adaptations due to short-term fluctuations in students' pre-requisites (Corno, 2008; Tetzlaff et al., 2021), such as individualized feedback or additional instructional support (van Braak et al., 2021; van de Pol et al., 2014, 2019).

1.2. Adaptive teaching with technology

Adaptive teaching puts high demands on teachers, as they must iteratively assess students' current learning progress to provide adaptations on the macro and the micro level which sought to be realized by technological advancement.

Prior research mainly focused adaptive learning systems and teacher dashboards when analyzing the impact of technology in adaptive classrooms. Computer-based intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) have been developed since the 1990s to assess learners' states and provide adaptive instruction to students, usually without requiring teachers to intervene (Aleven & Koedinger, 2002; Anderson et al., 1995; Brusilovsky et al., 1996; Burkhart et al., 2020; Graesser et al., 2004; Hui et al., 2020; Meurers et al., 2019). These intelligent tutoring systems comprise automatic assessments and instructional strategies to provide adaptive learning materials. Several meta-analyses demonstrated that ITS yield positive effects on learning (Hillmayr et al., 2020; Kulik & Fletcher, 2016; Ma et al.,

2014; Steenbergen-Hu & Cooper, 2014). For instance, Ma et al. (2014) obtained small to medium effects of ITS in their meta-analysis ($0.36 < g < 0.41$), depending on the type of analysis (fixed versus random effect model). Interestingly, effects of ITS were comparable to those of one-on-one human tutoring or small group discussions (VanLehn, 2011), suggesting that computer-based adaptive learning can effectively mimic tutoring.

Relatedly, teacher dashboards have been discussed as another computer-aided option to support assessing students' learning (Molenaar & Knoop-van Campen, 2019; van Leeuwen et al., 2019; Xhakaj et al., 2017). Teacher dashboards are visual displays that depict current information of students' learning processes on the individual or class-level to support teachers in monitoring students' individual or collaborative computer-based activities. Thus, teacher dashboards constitute an indirect form of teacher support, as they allow to automatically receive veridical judgments of learning progresses within computer-based learning environments (Zhu & Urhahne, 2018). On the downside, teachers consequently are not able to track students' learning beyond the online environment with teacher dashboards, such as in the current classroom situation. Keuning and van Geel (2021) conducted a cognitive task analysis and compared teachers' differentiation strategies when they had a dashboard available to more traditional contexts without having a dashboard available. The findings suggested that teachers' differentiation strategies on the macro-level were comparably effective, however, only small benefits occurred for using teacher dashboards regarding students' learning gains (Tissenbaum & Slotta, 2019).

Knoop-van Campen et al. (2021) analyzed teachers' micro-adaptations regarding the provision of process-oriented feedback compared to less effective task-oriented feedback. Results demonstrated that utilizing the dashboard led to a balanced proportion of task- and process-oriented feedback and a reduction of task-oriented feedback alone. Interestingly, the amount of feedback was more equally distributed among weaker and stronger students in class when the teachers used the dashboard, indicating that teacher dashboards may be particularly suited to support teachers in providing micro-adaptions at the class level.

1.3. The present study

Together, these findings provide important insights into how technology can contribute to adaptive teaching. However, they also highlight two crucial obstacles to use such technology for adaptive teaching. First, most adaptive learning systems were developed for only one specific topic. Second, there is a desiderate regarding the implementation of such technologies in the classroom, as most of the studies were restricted to the effectiveness of using such technologies. Thus, educational knowledge is needed whether and how technologies can be orchestrated in authentic classroom settings to provide adaptive learning opportunities across subjects (Lachner, Backfisch, & Franke, 2024; Scheiter, 2021).

That said, a general approach is missing, that contains options for the integration of non-subject related technology for all phases of adaptive teaching that can be realized in normal classrooms settings. Whether and how such a general approach of technology use for teaching adaptively is successful in terms of students' learning has not been investigated yet, likely because adaptive teaching with technology has mostly been investigated from a technological perspective, but not from a teaching perspective (Schmid et al., 2022). To explore the feasibility of technology use for adaptive teaching and to detect strengths but also potential pitfalls, a comprehensive examination is needed that contains diverse perspectives (Lachner et al., 2024b), such as on a student-level (e.g., learning gains) but also on a teacher-level (e.g., reflection on their perceived feasibility including strengths and pitfalls).

In this study, we aimed to close this research gap by developing teaching units ($N = 12$, see Table 1) with diverse topics in different subjects, based on our general framework of adaptive teaching with technology. We developed the units in collaboration with teachers who then taught the units in school. To examine the success of the teaching units, we analyzed students' (meta-)cognitive and motivational learning gains and interviewed teachers who reflected on the feasibility of technology use for adaptive teaching and its strengths and potential pitfalls.

The study was implemented within the project "DiA:GO", a multi-institutional collaboration initiative of educational researchers, school principals, and teachers from two high schools. Both schools were in the same borough in Southwestern Germany. The project was designed over a four-year period, during which the teachers were initially trained in adaptive teaching with technologies, so that in the second step they could develop technology-enhanced teaching units and test them in their own classes. The school's technology

Table 1
Overview of the teaching units

Teaching unit	School	Subject	Topic	Domain	Students	Grade level	Number of tasks in knowledge tests	Points per task	Maximal score in knowledge test
1	1	Mathematics	Functions	STEM	14	11	5	3	15
2	1	Mathematics	Statistics	STEM	14	12	6	4	24
3	1	Mathematics	Geometry	STEM	8	12	7	3	21
4	1	Physics	Electromagnetism	STEM	12	12	5	3	15
5	1	Chemistry	Redox	STEM	24	12	6	3	18
6	2	German	Romanticism	Language	16	11	3	6	18
7	2	German	Romanticism	Language	15	11	3	6	18
8	2	English	World of work	Language	16	11	3	6	18
9	2	English	World of work	Language	19	11	3	6	18
10	1	Spanish	Leisure activities	Language	18	11	6	3	18
11	1	Spanish	Past forms	Language	15	11	6	6	36
12	1	Ethics	Kant	Humanities	12	12	7	2	14

infrastructure and the familiarization with the topic took two years. The development of the teaching units, their implementation, and evaluation took place in the last two years of the project duration.

2. Method

2.1. Study design and study site

Because our main aim was to examine the feasibility and implementation conditions of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching as important precursors of instructional effectiveness, we did not apply a (quasi-)experimental design. We instead explored the feasibility of adaptive teaching within regular schooling by realizing a *sequential-explanatory mixed-methods design* (see Fig. 1; McCrudden et al., 2019; Plano Clark, 2019).

In the quantitative study, we first investigated students' meta-cognitive gains (change of accuracy of their judgement of learning), cognitive gains (change of learning outcomes), and motivational gains (change of interest) per teaching unit (following a pre-post-test design; see Fig. 2), as proxies for the feasibility of our teaching units. We additionally asked students to rate their self-efficacy and perceived usefulness of implementing educational technology in the specific subject in the pre- and post-evaluation as additional explanatory variables. To explore potential boundary conditions of the teaching feasibility, we conducted moderator analyses on an individual student-level (prior knowledge) and on the contextual classroom level (implementation fidelity, domain) to investigate potential implementation conditions of our framework. Based on aptitude-treatment-interaction effects, we investigated whether increases of the learning gains depended on a) students' prior knowledge, as a crucial pre-requisite of knowledge acquisition (Simonsmeier et al., 2022). At the same time, we investigated whether b) the domain of the teaching unit (STEM, languages, humanities) or c) the fidelity of the teaching units (implementation of adaptive teaching elements: formative assessment, macro adaptation, micro adaptation, consolidation phase; Sinha & Kapur, 2021) affected students' differences in learning, monitoring, and interest.

Based on the quantitative analyses, we conducted semi-structured interviews in the qualitative analysis with a sampling of three teachers whose teaching unit indicated a) very small, b) medium, and c) large learning gains in students (maximum variation sampling), aiming at exploring conditions of success and pitfalls of the feasibility of the teaching units by applying thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Finally, we merged the qualitative data (interview transcripts) with the quantitative results (Fig. 1) to further explore why some teaching units (those with large gains) were more feasible and beneficial than other teaching units (those with low gains), aiming at drawing conclusions on how to integrate educational technology in adaptive teaching settings effectively.

In total, 183 students from two local high schools in South-Western Germany participated in the study. Their mean age was 16.47 years ($SD = 1.42$), and 51 percent were female (Table 1). As determined by an a-priori-power analysis, we needed 90 participants to detect small to medium gains with a power of 0.80. We aimed to collect an additional 20 percent of participants to control for potential clustering effects, resulting in a minimum sample size of 108 students. Thus, our sample exceeded the required sample size. The three teachers who participated in the qualitative study were on average 33 years ($M = 33.00$; $SD = 3.74$) and had taught for about 5 years ($M = 5.33$; $SD = 3.30$) on average at the time of the interview (Table 2). Two of the teachers were male and one was female.

Fig. 1. Explanatory-sequential mixed-methods design.

Fig. 2. Pre-post-test-design of quantitative data collection.

2.2. Development of teaching units with Co-design and ManyClasses approaches

We followed the concept of *co-design* (Roschelle et al., 2006; Severance et al., 2016) to develop the technology-based and adaptive teaching units. Co-designs commonly differ from researcher-led “top-down approaches”, as they consider and integrate teachers’ everyday practices by actively involving them as agents in the process. Thus, teachers are seen as professional contributors and sources of educational development (Roschelle et al., 2006; Severance et al., 2016) which contribute to more applicable innovations (Severance et al., 2016).

To investigate the feasibility of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching and its boundary conditions, we adopted the co-design approach by Leinonen (2010; Fig. 3). In the first step, the *context inquiry phase*, we and the teachers designed a general and applicable framework (see Fig. 4) for innovative technology-supported adaptive teaching and its implementation into different subjects (STEM, languages, humanities). We conducted focus-group discussions with the school principals, teacher representatives, representatives of the school board, and the local technical administration to deeply understand the research and teaching contexts of the different schools (e.g., infrastructure at school, experience in adaptive teaching). In accordance with the school principals, eight teachers agreed to participate in the project. To enhance the co-design between research and practice, regular design workshops (N = 5–6 per year) were held to gain a mutual understanding of adaptive teaching (cf. Roschelle et al., 2006). These design workshops were the basis to develop a working model of adaptive teaching with educational technology, comprising four different phases as key elements of adaptive teaching (Fig. 4): formative assessments, adaptations on a micro-level, and adaptations on a macro level, including consolidation phases of the learned contents.

In the subsequent *participatory phase* (Fig. 3), researchers and teachers started to define the general conditions of the teaching units, such as duration, subject, topic, and learning aims. In the *product phase*, the researchers and teachers then collaboratively designed the teaching units. The teachers worked in tandems and provided formative feedback to each other from an educational practice perspective. The researchers contributed with evidence-based instructional strategies and approaches that have shown to be effective in research and supported the teachers with finding appropriate ways to support adaptive teaching by means technology. After the teaching unit was finalized, the teachers taught the unit in their regular lessons (duration: 3–4 weeks). Afterwards, in the *product release phase*, all lesson plans and materials were published as open educational resources (https://lms-public.uni-tuebingen.de/ilias3/goto_pr01_cat_6858.html).

One limitation of co-design approaches is that the obtained findings are tied to the material used and the context in which the learning environment was implemented. This makes it difficult to draw more general solutions, as learning and teaching are complex

Table 2
Qualitative sample.

	Low effect	Medium effect	Large effect
Pseudonym	Paul	Anna	David
Gender	Male	Female	Male
Age	38	29	32
Total years teaching	10	3	3
Domain of unit	Language	STEM	STEM
Students' grade	11	11	11
Effect of students' learning gains (<i>d</i>)	0.23	0.70	1.75
Implementation fidelity (Adaptivity)	1.86	2.60	2.87
Experience: Educational technology in classroom	High	Moderate	High
Relevance: Educational technology in classroom	High	Moderate	High
Experience: Adaptive teaching	Low	Moderate	Low
Relevance: Adaptive teaching	High	High	High

Fig. 3. Co-design process (based on Leinonen, 2010).

Fig. 4. Developed framework of adaptive teaching within co-design.

phenomena which are situated in a particular context. Co-design approaches can therefore only be seen as one single implementation of a learning and teaching principle (e.g., adaptive teaching with technology) under distinct and likewise restricted situations (Turner & Meyer, 2000).

The LoGeT-model (Lachner, Sibley, & Wagner, 2024) therefore suggests a combination of co-designs with a *ManyClasses approach*. The ManyClasses approach (Fyfe et al., 2021) addresses this shortcoming as implementing a common design framework across a variety and range of topics, teacher implementations, and student samples, which may help to understand whether distinct findings of

educational practices, such as technology-enhanced adaptive teaching, are generalizable and/or whether findings are determined by an individual student-level (prior knowledge) or a contextual classroom level (implementation fidelity, domain; Turner & Meyer, 2000).

2.3. Quantitative measures

2.3.1. Learning gains

As indicator for the feasibility of the teaching units, subject-specific knowledge tests were designed for each teaching unit to measure students' learning gains (pre-posttest-differences) as a dependent variable (item example for the chemistry unit: "Magnesium and sulfur react to form magnesium sulfide. State the oxidation, reduction, and redox reaction using reaction equations"). To strengthen the construct validity of our instruments, the knowledge tests were jointly constructed by subject-matter experts and experts of educational technology and methodology. Each test was aligned with the learning objectives of the teaching units. To reduce recognition effects, two parallel versions of the assessments were used as pre- and posttests (Gross et al., 2013). During the design of the test items, we followed a comparative approach and continuously inspected the comparability of the test versions across teaching units. Each test was coded by two independent raters. Interrater reliability was good to excellent among teaching units ($ICC_{2,1} \geq 0.81$). Reliability among the teaching units was $\omega \geq 0.63$, except for German: $\omega = 0.41$.

2.3.2. Monitoring accuracy

To measure students' monitoring accuracy as meta-cognitive outcome as the second dependent variable, we asked them to make judgments about their expected performance on the pre- and posttest: "How confident are you that you can answer questions to the text correctly?" (Baars et al., 2017; Prinz et al., 2018) on a scale from 0 % (not confident) to 100 % (absolutely confident, Jacob et al., 2020; 2022; Schleinschok et al., 2017). We calculated monitoring accuracy according to Schraw (2009) in terms of absolute differences by using the squared difference between students' estimated performance and their actual performance in the test: $(X_{\text{Judgment}} - X_{\text{Performance}})^2$. Values could vary between zero and $(100\%)^2 = 10,000$, whereas zero indicates an accurate judgment.

2.3.3. Situational subject-specific interest

We measured students' situational interest in the specific subject as the third dependent variable with three items (e.g., "Mathematics captures my attention") adapted from Knogler et al. (2015) on a scale from 1 "not at all" to 4 "completely" ($\alpha = 0.87$).

2.3.4. Implementation fidelity

As implementation fidelity is regarded as a crucial moderator of the relationship of an intervention (i.e., adaptive teaching) and the intended outcomes (Carroll et al., 2007), we developed an implementation fidelity score (Sinha & Kapur, 2021). The implementation fidelity score ($\alpha = 0.60$) aimed to reflect the degree to which the participating teachers considered adaptivity (formative assessment, macro- and micro-adaptations, consolidation phase), which commonly refers to the concept of adherence and dosage (Carroll et al., 2007). Two independent raters coded 50 percent of the teaching units (see Supplementary Material A) regarding their adaptivity from 1 ("not present") to 4 ("fully present"). As the agreement was high ($ICC = 0.91$), one rater coded the remaining units.

2.3.5. Self-efficacy of using educational technology

Self-efficacy of using educational technology in the specific subject was measured with three items (e.g., "I think that I can use educational technology properly to learn Mathematics") adapted from Backfisch et al. (2021) and Rigotti et al. (2008) on a scale from 1 "not at all" to 4 "completely" ($\alpha = 0.71$).

2.3.6. Usefulness of educational technology

To measure perceived usefulness of technology in the specific subject, we used two items (e.g., "In my opinion, educational technology is useful for Mathematics lessons") adapted from Backfisch et al. (2021) on a scale from 1 "not at all" to 4 "completely". Reliability was good ($\alpha = 0.86$).

2.3.7. Academic self-concept

To measure academic self-concept, we used six items (e.g., "I think that I can learn new content in Mathematics easily") by Frey et al. (2009) on a scale from 1 "not at all" to 4 "completely" ($\alpha = 0.90$).

2.4. Data collection and procedure

We received permission from our local research ethics committee, the regional school council, and the school principals to conduct the study. Additionally, we informed all school students and their legal guardians (e.g., parents) about the aim and procedure and collected their written consent to participate in the study. The participation was voluntary. Students who refused to participate could attend the teaching unit as usual without taking part in data collection. Thus, these participants had no disadvantages. All collected data was stored in line with the DSGVO guidelines on German servers.

2.4.1. Quantitative data

2.4.1.1. Procedure of Quantitative Data Collection. At the beginning of each teaching unit, students stated their age and gender and were asked to rate their academic self-concept in the subject, interest, self-efficacy of using educational technology in the specific subject, and the perceived usefulness to implement educational technology in the specific subject. Afterwards, they judged how many points they would receive in the subsequent knowledge test (judgement of learning) to compute the monitoring accuracy measures at the pretest. Then, students answered the pretest which took approximately 35 min. After completing the pretest, students participated in the developed teaching unit. The average duration of the units was three to four weeks, depending on the number of lessons conducted per week. At the end of each week, students rated the adaptivity of the lessons and their interest in the specific subject. At the end of the teaching units, students again judged their current knowledge, completed the posttest, rated their interest, self-efficacy, and the perceived usefulness to implement educational technology in the specific subject.²

2.4.1.2. Qualitative data analyses. As the study was implemented in schools across two time points, missing values occurred. We therefore applied multiple imputations with 50 imputed datasets and 50 iterations. Afterwards, we performed multiple regressions regarding students' learning gains, monitoring accuracy, and interest. As the data had a nested structure, we applied cluster-robust estimations of fixed effect models to account for the correlated error terms within a cluster (students within units) but independent error terms across clusters (Cameron & Miller, 2015). In model 1, we aimed to investigate the feasibility of the teaching units by estimating the gains of students' knowledge, monitoring accuracy, and interest (dependent variables) from pretest to posttest (measuring point as independent variable). To investigate potential boundary conditions, we added students' prior knowledge as moderator variable in model 2. We added the domain of the taught lesson units in model 3 and implementation fidelity in model 4 to further explore potential boundary conditions.

2.4.2. Qualitative data

2.4.2.1. Participating teachers. To form a maximum variation sample (Palinkas et al., 2016), based on the quantitative results, we selected three teachers whose teaching unit had a small, medium, and large learning gain to construct potential teacher profiles and to investigate potential implementation conditions via thematic analysis.

2.4.2.2. Procedure of qualitative data collection. The aim of the qualitative study was to explore strengths and pitfalls of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching. One student assistant, who received training (2 h), interviewed all three teachers individually while having semi-structured questions at hand and recorded the conversation on a local hard drive. We applied the following interview procedure: First, the assistant welcomed the teacher, introduced herself, and explained the aim of the interview. Teachers were asked about their prior experience (before joining the project) in a) using educational technology in the classroom and b) adaptive teaching. Second, they were asked to judge the relevance of both. Third, they reflected on their conducted teaching unit to explore patterns regarding pitfalls and success. The interviews took approximately 20 min. All three teachers provided written consent to participate in the interviews.

2.4.2.3. Qualitative data analysis. The first and second author jointly coded the scripted interviews in an iterative and inductive manner. We followed a peer debriefing strategy to enhance the trustworthiness of our findings and resolve potential differences by discussion. First, we focused on statements that reflected their prior experience (before joining the project) in a) using educational technologies in the classroom and b) adaptive teaching as well as their perceived relevance of both to create teachers' profile. Second, we explored the conducted teaching units in more detail by focusing on themes (see [Supplementary Material B](#)) that may explain differences in the feasibility across units (Schmidt et al., 2019).

We followed the six-step procedure by Braun and Clarke (2006) to ensure the quality of our analyses (see [Supplementary Material B](#) for excerpts of an audit trail). First, we familiarized ourselves with the interviews, and iteratively read them to detect specific themes and patterns that may have emerged. Second, we created initial codes to reduce the verbal data. Third, we combined codes to portray potential themes. Fourth, we reviewed the different themes to tell an accurate story of the data within the interviews. Fifth, we defined the themes and sixth included them in our report of the qualitative analyses. By using thematic analysis, we aimed at reflecting the conducted teaching units on a deeper level. As a further safeguard, we used the checklist by Braun and Clarke (2006) at the end of our analyses to heighten its quality. Due to the inductive and iterative coding approach, the calculation of inter-rater reliabilities, which are based on pre-given, deductive categories were not feasible in our study.

² We decided to not include the perceived usefulness and technology-related self-efficacy to enhance the comprehensiveness of the manuscript.

A

B

Fig. 5. A: Prior knowledge as moderator of students' learning gains

B: Implementation fidelity as moderator of students' learning gains

Note. The green area represents the standard estimation error of the smooth regression. The red dashed line highlights the intercepts to differentiate between positive values (increase) or negative values (decrease). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

3. Results

3.1. Quantitative results

3.1.1. Preliminary results

Before participating in the teaching units, students reported high usefulness ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.77$, scale from 1 to 4) and high self-efficacy ($M = 3.32$, $SD = 0.62$, scale from 1 to 4) in applying educational technology in the specific subject. Both remained stable on a high level during the teaching units ($\beta < -0.02$) suggesting that our students assessed themselves to be relatively proficient in using educational technologies. Additionally, students reported a medium to high subject-specific academic self-concept ($M = 2.77$, $SD = 0.30$, scale from 1 to 4).

3.1.2. Students' (Meta-)Cognitive and motivational learning gains

In model 1, we investigated potential gains in students' cognitive (comprehension), meta-cognitive (monitoring accuracy), and interest as indicators for the feasibility of the units (see [Appendix A](#) for correlation table and [Appendix B](#) for descriptive values). Results showed a small cognitive learning gain ($\beta = 0.22$, $p < 0.001$) from pre-to posttest. The variability between teaching units was considerably high ($ICC = 0.46$). No significant gains were found for students' monitoring accuracy ($\beta = -0.14$, $p = 0.141$, $ICC = 0.06$) and interest ($\beta = -0.07$, $p = 0.320$, $ICC = 0.28$).

3.1.3. Influence of boundary conditions

To investigate to what extent students' gains in learning, monitoring accuracy, and interest depended on student-related and context-related boundary conditions, we included students' individual differences (prior knowledge), domain, and implementation fidelity as subsequent moderators in our analyses ([Appendix C](#)).

Results of model 2 indicated that prior knowledge was a significant moderator regarding students' learning gains ($\beta = -0.20$, $p = 0.020$, small effect). Particularly students with low prior knowledge had higher gains after participating in the teaching units than students with higher levels of prior knowledge ([Fig. 5A](#)). In model 3, the moderation effect of prior knowledge, however, disappeared when including domain as moderator ([Appendix C](#)). At the same time, domain did not moderate the effect. In model 4, we included implementation fidelity as the final moderator. Indeed, implementation fidelity moderated students' learning gains ($\beta = 0.13$, $p = 0.020$, small effect). Students benefited more from the teaching units that showed high levels of adaptivity than from units with low levels of adaptivity ([Fig. 5B](#)). Regarding monitoring accuracy and interest, none of the moderators approached significance ([Appendix C](#)).

3.2. Qualitative results

3.2.1. Underlying processes of teaching units

The quantitative analyses revealed two interesting findings. First, all adaptive teaching units were not equally successful. While some teaching units allowed students to strongly increase their knowledge, other teaching units barely improved students' learning. Second, the feasibility of the units seemed to depend on their implementation fidelity. These results arise the questions why some teaching units were so successful while other were not. Even though all teaching units were based on the same model, they were implemented in different ways. Additionally, teachers' experiences in teaching adaptively and with technology may have affected the teaching units differently. To explore the conditions of success, we applied semi-structured interviews with a maximum variation sample of the teaching units regarding their effectiveness. We chose to interview teachers whose teaching units resulted in a) small, b) medium, and c) large learning gains of students ([Table 2](#)). First, we asked the teachers what experiences they had before they joined the project a) in using educational technology in classrooms and b) in teaching adaptively. Additionally, we asked them about their perceived relevance of educational technology and adaptive teaching. We used the information to build a teacher profile based on their prior experiences and beliefs. Second, we asked them to reflect on their conducted teaching unit in terms of a) strengths and b) pitfalls. In the following, we briefly describe the teaching units (see [Supplementary Material A](#) for more details), the teacher's profile, and their perceived strengths and pitfalls of the teaching unit. The main results are highlighted in italic words. Examples of excerpts of the audit trails and detailed steps of the thematic analysis can be found in the [Supplementary Material B](#). All quotes were translated to English.

3.2.2. Paul's teaching unit (low effect)

Paul started his teaching unit with a formative assessment and then provided the students with an online scavenger hunt to learn a new verb and its conjugation. In this scavenger hunt, students could learn in a self-regulated manner, for instance, by repeating parts which they did not understand. At the end of the teaching unit, students were engaged in a consolidation phase in which all new learning contents were discussed and repeated. Although Paul included adaptive parts in his teaching unit, adaptivity of this unit was low since he only conducted one formative assessment, and adaption on a macro-level, and one consolidation phase (see [Supplementary Material A](#)). The poor adaptivity of the teaching unit is also reflected in the implementation fidelity score of 1.86 (on a scale from 1 to 4; see [Table 2](#)). Thus, apparently Paul's teaching unit did not only show little learning increases but also contained only few adaptive elements.

3.2.2.1. Paul's profile. We classified Paul's prior experience in using educational technology in class as *high* (Table 2), since Paul reported that he "got involved in that style of teaching" with educational technology out of interest and even "hold workshops and lectures on this topic" for teachers. For five years, he has been working as an "multiplier for the digitalization initiative of the state of Baden-Württemberg and was a teacher educator specialized in educational technology. We additionally assumed that Paul considered educational technology for learning processes, before joining the research project as *highly relevant* (Table 2), because he stated that educational technology in schools is fundamental and that "you should not ask yourself the question [about technology in class] at all anymore", as educational technologies "are simply omnipresent" in students' daily life. He was also enthusiastic about using educational technology in classrooms, as he believed that it "offers very, very big opportunities to really do something innovative" in the context of learning and continually repeated its "insanely important value". At the same time, he stated that educational technology should be used "in a meaningful way" and seemed to be aware of an efficient way of using it for learning processes.

Furthermore, Paul stated to have "no experience" in adaptive teaching before he joined the project. Thus, we concluded that Paul had *no* prior experience but determined Paul's perceived relevance of adaptive teaching as *high* (Table 2), since he stated that he considered adaptive teaching as "incredibly important". He said that adaptive teaching is particularly important since "schools with heterogeneous students aim at individualized learning" which however "has hopelessly overwhelmed" the teachers. Compared to individualized learning, Paul considered adaptive teaching as a "profit" as "adaptions on a macro level facilitate the preparation and offer of learning materials", as the teacher must "offer only three, four, or five different levels of learning materials but not 25 different levels".

3.2.2.2. Strengths of Paul's teaching unit. Regarding strengths of his unit, we determined *teachers' mindset* and *students' motivation*, since Paul mentioned that it is important for a teacher to be "open for new ways of thinking" and to "motivate students to learn". For achieving the latter, following a game-based learning approach (Sailer & Homner, 2020), he implemented an "online scavenger hunt" (that is a combination of riddles and tasks based on previously learned contents, aiming at finding a treasure) in which "students fought against the evil dwarf Coronix" by answering questions. Paul highlighted the digital scavenger hunt as very successful, as students were not only "motivated to actively participate" but also because he "could collect both quantitative data, for instance by means of correct-wrong-tasks, and qualitative data with audio files" of the students. Additionally, to *realize macro-adaptions*, Paul assigned students based on their performance into "different levels of difficulty within the scavenger hunt". Students were "able to repeat the hunt and also to change levels".

3.2.2.3. Pitfalls of Paul's teaching unit. Regarding pitfalls, we concluded that Paul strongly focused on individualized learning with a *lack of consolidation phases*. Students only learned individually and without any consolidation activities with the entire class during using the scavenger hunt tool. We came to this conclusion as Paul stated that he struggled with tracking students' learning process and did not know whether students understood the contents adequately. He was unsure in how to "bring the students back together again". We assumed that this may be particularly the case as his unit showed a *lack of regular formative assessments*. He only realized one single assessment to assess students' learning, namely at the beginning of the unit. Paul concluded that he would implement more formative assessments in a future unit, not only to track learning processes but also to provide students with materials based on their current knowledge (macro adaptations).

Additionally, the teaching unit might reflect a *low level of difficulty*, meaning that it had been too easy for the students. We draw this conclusion as Paul stated that he "would make the unit more difficult" next time. "More difficult in the sense of different grammatical structures". Thus, students might not have been challenged enough which may have led to the little learning increases.

Another interesting point was the integration of technology. Paul stated that he may have used *too many educational technology formats* and that he would use less in future units. The excessive use of educational technology may have provided an additional burden and induced extraneous processing for students who had to learn the functionalities of different technologies which could be detrimental for learning.

In total, the qualitative analysis revealed that Paul's approach of individualized learning seemed to be motivating for students and provided advantages, as he was able to collect students' quantitative and qualitative data. However, the use of several technologies may have resulted in extraneous processing and was therefore likely a trade-off regarding students' learning. Additionally, regular formative assessments and consolidation phase were missing which may have reduced the fit between the students' abilities and the provided learning materials.

3.2.3. Anna's teaching unit (medium effect)

Anna started her teaching unit with a cognitive activation in form of a brainstorming task which she used to assess students' current knowledge (formative assessment). Then, students were engaged in different learning phases in which they learned the new contents with interactive working sheets in a self-regulated manner. Finally, they deepened their understanding by generating an explanatory video or by conducting an experiment to answer a research question. Students could choose one of the two options (macro-adaption) to increase their motivation (see Deci & Ryan, 2000). All generated outcomes were discussed (consolidation phase). In total, Anna implemented two formative assessments, one adaption on a macro-level, and three consolidation phases (see Supplementary Material A). Her efforts in teaching adaptively are also reflected in the implementation fidelity score of 2.60 (on a scale from 1 to 4; see Table 2). Thus, Anna's teaching unit did not only result in higher learning outcomes but also higher levels of adaptivity compared to Paul's teaching unit.

3.2.3.1. Anna's profile. We classified Anna as having a *moderate* prior experience in applying educational technology in the classroom before joining the project (Table 2), as she uttered to have relatively few experiences in using educational technology in classrooms but uses educational technology “for basic teaching methods”. For instance, she prepares “worksheets on the computer”, “employ[s] animations” for specific lessons but uses her “tablet very little”. Additionally, we concluded that Anna considered educational technology as *moderately relevant* for learning (Table 2) since she, on the one hand, stated that educational technologies “are a great, great benefit in STEM”, especially because of “many great animations which guide students step by step through a process”. On the other hand, she argued that educational technology is predominantly not suited in learning tasks that “focus on discussions”.

Regarding her prior experience in adaptive teaching, we assumed that Anna had *moderate* experience (Table 2) as she did not demonstrate an explicit scientific concept of adaptive teaching but “regularly integrate[s] adaptive elements without thinking about it”. Regarding its relevance, we concluded that Anna considered adaptive teaching as *highly relevant* (Table 2), since she stated that adaptivity is “very important” and the “gold standard of teaching in future”, particularly for teachers in a “high school with students with very heterogeneous backgrounds”.

3.2.3.2. Strengths of Anna's teaching unit. When asking Anna about conditions of success regarding implementing educational technology in adaptive learning settings, she referred to the infrastructure and argued that it is fundamental that “the school provides good conditions”, for instance, that “every student has his/her own tablet” and “sockets in each classroom”. Additionally, “students need technological knowledge about how to use educational technology”. In her school, Anna reported that the “conditions were perfect”, so we assumed that these *good technological conditions* in school facilitated the realization of the teaching unit. Moreover, we concluded that the *use of educational technology* is an important factor to realize adaptive teaching in school, since Anna highlighted that educational technology was essential for applying adaptive elements, such as assigning different difficulty levels to students. She also stated that educational technology was essential to teach adaptively in her unit, as without educational technology “students would not be able to learn in a self-regulated manner”.

We determined her *flexible response towards students' needs* and *consolidation phase* as additional strengths of Anna's teaching unit, as she reported that she “spontaneously used one lesson to explain the contents and to bring students back together” when she had the feeling of losing track on their current learning process. Moreover, we determined *experimental learning* and *adaptations on the macro-level* as additional strengths: In Anna's unit, students learned the contents by using animations. As a final project, students individually conducted a virtual experiment or created a video about the learned contents. Anna reported that she provided the students with different opportunities in completing the project. Students could “choose different experiments that differed in their levels of difficulty”. Anna reported that “students had a lot of fun working on their projects” and that she would implement such experimental projects in a future unit again.

3.2.3.3. Pitfalls of Anna's teaching unit. Regarding potential pitfalls, we determined the same pitfall of a *lack of formative assessments and consolidation* of the learned contents like in Paul's unit. Even though Anna reported that she tried to keep track by “taking time for questions at the beginning and end of each lesson”, aiming at assessing students' current knowledge “like an intermediate assessment”, she had “troubles to provide students with essential information” and was wondering “how to control students' learning”. She additionally stated that she would realize another formative assessment “in the middle of the unit” in the future to control if students “actually learned the contents correctly”. Thus, we concluded that she felt unsure regarding what students had learned in self-regulated phases, as she lost track of their current learning process. Apparently, taking time for questions is not enough to assess students' current knowledge.

Moreover, Anna mentioned a *lack of guidelines* as another pitfall since “students were overloaded with learning the contents by themselves” in the student-centered learning phase. Anna said that she would therefore “provide the key information in a more structured way” containing “smaller steps with more details” in a future unit. Additionally, we detected *time* as a last potential pitfall since Anna said that developing and implementing new teaching concepts “is very time consuming”.

In total, we concluded that flexibility (e.g., Anna's spontaneous consolidation phase), more formative assessments to track students' current learning, and adaptation to students' needs (e.g., more guidelines) were essential factors for the success of the teaching unit.

3.2.4. David's teaching unit (large effect)

David started his teaching unit with a brainstorming task as a cognitive activation. He used the results as a formative assessment and provided students with working sheets to learn the new contents. He discussed and consolidated the results at the end of the lesson (consolidation phase). In his teaching unit, students learned in a self-regulated manner with worksheets, experiments, and simulations. David regularly implemented formative assessments to provide students with materials based on their needs but also consolidation phases to keep the class together. In total, David implemented three formative assessments, one adaptation on a macro-level, and three consolidation phases (see [Supplementary Material A](#)). The implementation fidelity score of 2.87 (on a scale from 1 to 4; see Table 2) is higher than the score of Paul's and Anna's teaching unit. Thus, David's teaching unit did not only result in the highest learning outcomes but also in the highest level of adaptivity.

3.2.4.1. David's profile. We classified David's prior experience in using educational technology in classroom as *high* (see Table 2) since he reported to have “considerable experience”. Additionally, he stated to be “personally interested” in educational technology and that his lessons are “entirely based on tablets”. Regarding the relevance of educational technology in classroom, we concluded that David

considered educational technology as *highly relevant* for learning, as he repeatedly stated that educational technology is “very important” in STEM subjects but also in other subjects since technologies “offer so many opportunities in classroom, for example, sharing students’ screens to demonstrate their results or research and to realize formative assessments”, or for conducting digital experiments and simulations which would be “too expensive” in real life. Additionally, David said that the use of educational technology in school “is very useful”, since “this generation of students deals with technology in their daily lives.

Nevertheless, we assumed that David has a more pragmatic view, compared to Paul who was more enthusiastic about the use of educational technology, since David mentioned several times that educational technology offers great potentials, but also have limitations in specific teaching scenarios. He, for instance, reported that “making sketches does not work well on tablets, as students have to switch between two programs – the work sheet or the sketch program”. He additionally highlighted that educational technology is “incredibly useful” only when it is used to reach “special aims” to enhance teaching quality.

David stated that he had “no” experience in adaptive teaching before starting the project. Thus, we classified him to have *low* prior experience in adaptive teaching (see Table 2). Regarding the relevance of adaptive teaching, we concluded that David perceived teaching adaptively as *highly relevant*, since he said it is “very, very important” and “incredibly important, particularly in schools with heterogenous students”. He highlighted that “it is the most important thing” that “every student gets the opportunity learn at their own level”. However, he also mentioned that it is important “to find a balance between effort and benefit” of using educational technology in the classroom.

3.2.4.2. Strengths of David’s teaching unit. Regarding strengths, we concluded that *experimental learning* and *individual learning in combination with several guidelines* may have helped students in their learning process, since David reported that he provided students “with many virtual experiments, about eight” and provided “different kinds of guidelines and support options, [...] such as videos” so that “students were able to work through the virtual experiments individually and in their own pace”. He said that this approach “worked very well” and that “students worked independently, even though they had little experience in experimental learning”. David stated that this student-centered learning phase might have worked so well since all “guidelines were very detailed” and because he was “present and adjusted” the materials during the unit.

We determined *flexible* reactions as another condition of success since David reported that he “created [his] own tools” in cases when he “did not find an appropriate tool”. He said that he “used PowerPoint to create tasks including different pictures and hyperlinks” as guidelines and that “students worked [with these guidelines] very well”.

Additionally, we determined *regular realization of several formative assessments* as another strength since David stated that he realized several formative assessments “on the fly” to “keep track on students’ learning process and to be able to provide them with feedback”. Interestingly, he only used educational technology once (at the beginning of the unit) for realizing a formative assessment as he reported that it “is time consuming and difficult to realize during a unit”. He said that he then realized “informal formative assessments” instead, which he “did not need to prepare and could be realized flexibly”.

3.2.4.3. Pitfalls of David’s teaching unit. Regarding pitfalls, we concluded that *testing students’ access to tools* in advance is essential for the success of the teaching unit. David reported most of the students could not work with his PowerPoint guidelines since they did not have an account for this program. We additionally determined a *lack of details in guidelines* as a potential pitfall, since David reported that students struggled with the “documentation of the experiments”. He “provided them with a template but they did not know how to use it” and therefore would “improve the guidelines” next time.

In total, David’s teaching unit might have resulted in high feasibility since he provided students with detailed guidelines (except for one time), realized regular formative assessments, and was flexibly responsive towards students’ needs and the general conditions in the classroom.

4. Discussion

The main aim of the current explanatory-sequential mixed-methods study was to investigate the feasibility of technology-based adaptive teaching and its boundary conditions across different subjects on an individual student-level (prior knowledge) and on a contextual classroom level (domain, implementation fidelity). We combined a quantitative and a qualitative study, which we see as a clear strength of our study as the combination allows rich insights into technology-enhanced adaptive teaching.

From a quantitative perspective, we obtained small cognitive learning gains, but no significant changes regarding students’ monitoring accuracy and interest. These findings suggest that adaptive teaching affects cognitive, but not monitoring and motivational changes; probably because they are rather stable constructs, which are resistant to change (Rieger et al., 2017; Roeschl-Heils et al., 2003).

The moderation analyses further indicated that prior knowledge and implementation fidelity (the degree to which technology is exploited towards processes of adaptive teaching) are crucial to support students’ learning. The effect of prior knowledge is interesting, as it contrasts with the common Matthew effect (see Simonsmeier et al., 2021; for critical discussion), which postulates that strong students profit from instructional interventions more than weaker students. Contrarily, our findings add to the scarce evidence that low-prior knowledge students may profit from adaptive environments (Hammer et al., 2021). However, we must note that the overall moderation effect of prior knowledge diminished when controlling for domain and implementation fidelity, meaning that adaptive teaching was comparably effective for students with low and high prior knowledge when taking the domain and level of adaptivity into account. Whether and to what extent technology plays a role in supporting low-prior knowledge students is still an open question.

Implementation fidelity as moderator highlights the critical role of considering adaptive elements for teaching. Nevertheless, the obtained findings are only a coarse proxy towards the feasibility of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching (Sinha & Kapur, 2021), as they are only correlative. More causal designs (e.g., randomized-controlled-field-trials, Gaspard et al., 2021; Iterbeke et al., 2021) are required to test the effectiveness of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching.

The qualitative analyses allowed even more details regarding the crucial role of implementation fidelity. Qualitative results revealed that particularly regular formative assessments were essential to teach adaptively. It is, however, important *how* teachers realize formative assessments since Anna's approach of taking time for questions did not assess all students' learning processes and therefore was not successful. Additionally, consolidation phases are needed to avoid individualized learning and to bring the class back together after self-regulated learning phases.

Thus, the qualitative analyses showed the need to incorporate regular formative assessments and consolidation phases to provide a considerable fit between students' individual needs and the provided learning activities (Furtak et al., 2016). From a theoretical perspective, these findings are interesting, as they clearly demonstrate that adaptive teaching is not necessarily effective, but depends on boundary conditions, for instance, whether and how adaptive teaching is realized with educational technology. This finding supports prior research which demonstrated that students' learning depends on the quality and not frequency of technological use in classrooms (Fütterer et al., 2022).

In this context, our qualitative analyses indicate that the combination of technological and pedagogical knowledge and motivation are crucial for realizing technology-enhanced adaptive teaching. The combination of quantitative and qualitative data revealed that teachers' technology experience is not enough to provide successful adaptive teaching units (i.e., Paul's profile). It is essential to have knowledge in using technology but also to show high levels of pedagogical knowledge (i.e., David's profile). This is in line with recent studies, which documented high correlations between motivation, professional knowledge, and the teaching quality when using technology for teaching (Backfisch et al., 2020, 2021).

Last, our qualitative findings highlight that adaptive teaching is not necessarily individualized instruction, as teachers require distinct assessment and conflation phases with the entire class to further proceed with adaptive teaching. Contrarily to commonly held beliefs, adaptive teaching is not a simple scaling up of individualized instruction (Corno, 2008; Vogt & Rogalla, 2009), but rather constitutes a blend of individualized instruction (e.g., formative assessment, adaptations) with classic instruction (e.g., direct instruction, classroom discussion). Nevertheless, these findings should be augmented with experimental field studies, which experimentally vary the presence or absence of distinct phases of adaptive teaching.

From a practical perspective, our quantitative findings are interesting as they indicate that our teaching units indeed provided the needed support for students with low prior knowledge and may therefore serve as good practice examples for adaptive teaching. Additionally, the results highlighted the essential need for regular formative assessments to a) understand students' current learning processes and needs, and b) adapt instructions and materials appropriately. In this context, it has been demonstrated that formative assessments do not necessarily need to rely on technology; they also proved beneficial when implemented in traditional ways, such as through questioning. Another practical result pertains to the core concept of adaptive teaching: Teachers who employed adaptive approaches, focusing on the class as a whole, demonstrated greater gains in student learning compared to those who primarily pursued individualized teaching. Thus, teachers should leverage the benefits of adaptive teaching (e.g., collaboration) while avoiding technologies that result in prolonged individualized learning phases.

We published our teaching units as open educational resources (https://lms-public.uni-tuebingen.de/ilias3/goto_pr01_cat_6858.html), so that they can be used and further developed for authentic classroom teaching (Lachner et al., -a2021). We see a clear benefit in our co-design approach for developing new adaptive teaching units, as we bridged theory and practice and melt them into research-based teaching units. Twelve teaching units were designed based on the same theoretical framework, namely focusing on technology-enhanced adaptivity. This iteration in various subjects allowed us to test the generalizability of our approach in educational practice and provides the feasibility of adaptive teaching with technology which are transferable into diverse settings (Fyfe et al., 2021).

4.1. Limitations

Our aim was to test the feasibility of technology-enhanced adaptive teaching and its boundary conditions and not to investigate the effectiveness of adaptive teaching with technology, which would require a control group. Although our moderation analyses pointed in the direction of implementation fidelity and suggested that higher implementation fidelity contributed to higher learning gains, further studies with larger sample sizes and an experimental setting are needed to investigate the causal role of educational technologies to enhance adaptive teaching.

Additionally, it remains unclear which facet of adaptivity led to the support of low-achieving students. Even though we collected data of adaptive elements on a micro-, macro-, formative assessment, and consolidation level, we were unable to investigate whether students benefitted from, for instance, additional materials (e.g., additional instructions) or from adaptive learning materials (e.g., adaptive learning systems). Future research is needed to identify the mechanisms of adaptivity in more detail.

Furthermore, the use of log files, video analysis, or student interviews could portray the underlying learning processes during adaptive teaching in addition to teacher interviews. An analysis of the mediating role of learning processes would help to better understand the mechanisms of adaptive teaching on students' cognitive and metacognitive learning (Tetzlaff et al., 2021).

4.2. Conclusion

All in all, by blending quantitative and qualitative findings in our mixed-methods study, we gained a better understanding of potentials and boundary conditions of using technology for adaptive teaching in authentic classrooms. Our findings highlight the role of implementation conditions and individual student conditions for realizing technology-enhanced adaptive teaching. Additionally, they may provide a starting point for educational practice for further developing adaptive teaching to productively encounter heterogeneity.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leonie Sibley: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andreas Lachner:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Christine Plicht:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Armin Fabian:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Iris Backfisch:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Katharina Scheiter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thorsten Bohl:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

<https://osf.io/wu6a3/>.

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Appendix A

	Comprehension gains	Monitoring gains	Interest gains
Comprehension gains	–	–	–
Monitoring gains	–0.14	–	–
Interest gains	–0.03	0.08	–

Note. Significant correlations are highlighted in bold.

Appendix B

Teaching unit	Subject	Learning outcome		Monitoring accuracy		Interest	
		Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
1	Mathematics	16.67 (10.86)	54.52 (22.33)	1806.35 (1142.96)	358.33 (599.35)	2.57 (0.36)	2.67 (0.28)
2	Mathematics	35.42 (10.99)	58.63 (10.52)	773.81 (819.01)	415.43 (543.20)	2.90 (0.44)	2.50 (0.75)
3	Mathematics	46.73 (10.18)	57.44 (11.27)	54.56 (76.65)	176.45 (122.39)	2.38 (0.52)	2.17 (0.25)
4	Physics	20.61 (11.53)	36.36 (5.47)	359.60 (487.10)	145.45 (184.56)	3.58 (0.56)	3.18 (0.75)
5	Chemistry	18.77 (6.80)	24.93 (10.94)	1071.94 (1217.22)	331.92 (480.34)	2.93 (0.77)	2.67 (0.61)
6	German	37.78 (10.59)	49.63 (8.84)	1379.63 (1253.44)	657.41 (1216.31)	2.33 (0.40)	2.44 (0.60)
7	German	48.21 (10.08)	51.50 (11.60)	679.56 (879.05)	962.13 (891.67)	2.17 (0.41)	1.85 (0.54)
8	English	64.81 (10.84)	68.89 (10.30)	216.05 (346.60)	219.14 (264.92)	3.02 (0.66)	3.20 (0.61)
9	English	70.14 (16.18)	64.22 (18.03)	1085.07 (1920.44)	442.54 (519.99)	2.31 (0.87)	2.45 (0.84)
10	Spanish	42.87 (20.19)	47.06 (16.76)	925.48 (1307.63)	614.5 (532.50)	3.02 (0.61)	3.03 (0.52)
11	Spanish	27.55 (13.23)	30.97 (8.59)	847.16 (1132.26)	781.06 (1025.84)	2.97 (0.63)	2.53 (0.69)
12	Ethics	40.00 (18.50)	50.79 (22.71)	693.88 (618.45)	566.89 (624.06)	2.07 (0.62)	2.33 (0.47)

Note. Learning outcomes are in percent. Values can vary from 0 to 100 %. Monitoring accuracy is calculated in absolute values. Values can vary from 0 (accurate judgement) to 10,000. Interest is represented on a scale from 1 (not at all interesting) to 4 (completely interesting).

Appendix C

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3			Model 4		
	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Comprehension												
Measuring point (pre-post)	0.22	0.05	<0.001	0.23	0.05	<0.001	0.23	0.05	<0.001	0.23	0.05	<0.001
Prior knowledge				0.60	0.10	<0.001	0.58	0.11	<0.001	0.57	0.11	<0.001
Measuring point \times Prior knowledge				-0.20	0.08	0.020	-0.17	0.10	0.090	-0.18	0.10	0.081
Domain							-0.06	0.09	0.526	-0.12	0.09	0.152
Measuring point \times Domain							0.06	0.07	0.346	0.00	0.07	0.997
Implementation fidelity										0.13	0.09	0.140
Measuring point \times Implementation fidelity										0.13	0.06	0.020
Monitoring accuracy												
Measuring point (pre-post)	-0.14	0.09	0.141	-0.14	0.09	0.143	-0.14	0.09	0.144	-0.14	0.09	0.144
Prior knowledge				-0.05	0.12	0.681	-0.09	0.13	0.512	-0.09	0.13	0.514
Measuring point \times Prior knowledge				0.10	0.11	0.390	0.08	0.12	0.518	0.08	0.12	0.506
Domain							-0.09	0.08	0.251	-0.07	0.08	0.404
Measuring point \times Domain							-0.04	0.06	0.527	-0.01	0.07	0.883
Implementation fidelity										-0.05	0.09	0.544
Measuring point \times Implementation fidelity										-0.06	0.07	0.370
Interest												
Measuring point (pre-post)	-0.07	0.07	0.321	-0.07	0.07	0.323	-0.07	0.07	0.322	-0.07	0.07	0.321
Prior knowledge				-0.08	0.10	0.455	-0.01	0.12	0.929	-0.01	0.12	0.951
Time \times Prior knowledge				0.09	0.08	0.276	0.06	0.09	0.929	0.07	0.20	0.499
Domain							0.16	0.10	0.120	0.20	0.09	0.029
Time \times Domain							-0.06	0.06	0.323	-0.09	0.07	0.170
Implementation fidelity										-0.09	0.09	0.326
Time \times Implementation fidelity										0.07	0.06	0.226

Note. Significant results are highlighted in bold.

Appendix D. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2024.105108> (<https://osf.io/wu6a3/>).

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